

RANDOM B_h SETS AND ADDITIVE BASES IN \mathbb{Z}_N

Csaba Sándor¹

Department of Stochastics, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary
 csandor@math.bme.hu

Received: 12/22/06, Revised: 6/20/07, Accepted: 6/22/07, Published: 7/3/07

Abstract

We determine a threshold function for B_h and additive basis properties in \mathbb{Z}_n .

1. Introduction

We use the following notations: \mathbb{Z} denotes the integers $0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$; \mathbb{N} is the set of positive integers; \mathbb{Z}_n is the additive cyclic group of order n . Members of a set S are referred to as $\{s_1, s_2, \dots\}$. The cardinality of a finite set S is denoted by $|S|$. A multiset $\mathbf{q} = \{q_1, \dots, q_k\}_m$ can be formally defined as a pair (Q, m) , where Q is the set of distinct elements of \mathbf{q} and $m : Q \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, where $m(q)$ is the multiplicity of $q \in \mathbf{q}$ for each $q \in Q$. The number of distinct elements of \mathbf{q} is denoted by $|\mathbf{q}|_d$. The usual set operations such as union, intersection and Cartesian product can be easily generalized for multisets. In this paper we use the intersection: suppose that (A, m) and (B, n) are multisets, then the intersection can be defined as $(A \cap B, f)$, where $f(x) = \min\{m(x), n(x)\}$.

For a given $S \subset \mathbb{Z}_n$ and $x \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ denote by $r_{S,h}(x)$ the number of different representations $x = s_1 + \dots + s_h$ with $s_i \in S$, that is

$$r_{S,h}(x) = |\{\{s_1, \dots, s_h\}_m : s_1 + \dots + s_h = x, \quad s_i \in S\}|.$$

A set $S \subset \mathbb{Z}_n$ is called B_h set if the number of distinct representation of x as $s_1 + \dots + s_h$, $s_i \in S$ is at most 1, that is $r_{S,h}(x) \leq 1$ for all $x \in \mathbb{Z}_n$. A set $S \subset \mathbb{Z}_n$ is called additive h -basis if every element in \mathbb{Z}_n can be represented as the sum of not necessarily distinct h elements of the set S , that is $r_{S,h}(x) \geq 1$ for every $x \in \mathbb{Z}_n$.

For n a positive integer, let $0 \leq p_n \leq 1$. The random subset $S(n, p_n)$ is a probabilistic space over the set of subsets of \mathbb{Z}_n determined by $Pr(k \in S_n) = p_n$ for every $k \in \mathbb{Z}_n$,

¹Supported by Hungarian National Foundation for Scientific Research, Grant No. T 49693 and 61908.

with these events being mutually independent. This model is often used for proving the existence of certain sequences. Given any combinatorial number theoretic property P , there is a probability that $S(n, p_n)$ satisfies P , which we write $Pr\{S(n, p_n) \models P\}$. The function $r(n)$ is called a threshold function for a combinatorial number theoretic property P if

- (i) When $p_n = o(r(n))$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Pr\{S(n, p_n) \models P\} = 0$,
- (ii) When $r(n) = o(p(n))$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Pr\{S(n, p_n) \models P\} = 1$,

or visa versa.

The goal of this paper is to determine a threshold function for B_h sets and additive h -bases in \mathbb{Z}_n . We use the typical notation $\exp(x) = e^x$

Theorem 1.1. *Let $c > 0$ be arbitrary. Let us suppose that $p_n = \frac{c}{n^{2h}}$ and the random set $A_n \subset \mathbb{Z}_n$ is defined the following way: For every $k \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ we have $Pr(k \in A_n) = p_n$. Then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Pr\{A_n \text{ is a } B_h \text{ set}\} = \exp\left(-\frac{c^{2h}}{2(h!)^2}\right)$.*

Theorem 1.2. *Let c be an arbitrary real number. Suppose that $p_n = \frac{(h!n \log n)^{1/h}(1 + \frac{c}{h \log n})}{n}$ and the random set $A_n \subset \mathbb{Z}_n$ is defined the following way: For every $k \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ we have $Pr\{k \in A_n\} = p_n$. Then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Pr(A_n \text{ is an additive } h\text{-basis}) = \exp(-\exp(-c))$.*

2. Proofs

In order to prove the theorems we need two lemmas from probability theory (see e.g. [1] p. 41, 95-98.). In many instances, we would like to bound the probability that none of the bad events $B_i, i \in I$, occur. If the events are mutually independent, then $Pr(\cap_{i \in I} \overline{B}_i) = \prod_{i \in I} Pr(\overline{B}_i)$. When the B_i are "mostly" independent, the Janson's inequality allows us, sometimes, to say that these two quantities are "nearly" equal. Let Ω be a finite universal set and R be a random subset of Ω given by $Pr(r \in R) = p_r$, these events being mutually independent over $r \in \Omega$. Let $E_i, i \in I$ be subsets of Ω , where I a finite index set. Let B_i be the event $E_i \subset R$. Let X_i be the indicator random variable for B_i and $X = \sum_{i \in I} X_i$ be the number of E_i s contained in R . The event $\cap_{i \in I} \overline{B}_i$ and $X = 0$ are then identical. For $i, j \in I$, we write $i \sim j$ if $i \neq j$ and $E_i \cap E_j \neq \emptyset$. We define $\Delta = \sum_{i \sim j} Pr(B_i \cap B_j)$, here the sum is over ordered pairs. We set $M = \prod_{i \in I} Pr(\overline{B}_i)$.

Lemma 1.3 (Janson's inequality). *Let $B_i, i \in I, \Delta, M$ be as above and assume that $Pr(B_i) \leq \epsilon$ for all i . Then*

$$M \leq Pr\left(\bigcap_{i \in I} \overline{B}_i\right) \leq M \exp\left(\frac{1}{1 - \epsilon} \cdot \frac{\Delta}{2}\right).$$

The more traditional approach to the Poisson paradigm is called Brun’s sieve, for its use by the number theorist T. Brun. Let F_1, \dots, F_m be events, X_i the indicator random variable for F_i , and $X = X_1 + \dots + X_m$ the number of B_i that hold. Let there be a hidden parameter n (so that actually $m = m(n), B_i = B_i^{(n)}, X = X^{(n)}$) which will define our O notations. Define

$$S^{(r)} = \sum Pr\{B_{i_1} \wedge \dots \wedge B_{i_r}\},$$

where the sum is over all sets $\{i_1, \dots, i_r\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, m\}$. The inclusion-exclusion principle gives that $Pr\{X = 0\} = Pr\{\overline{B_1} \wedge \dots \wedge \overline{B_m}\} = 1 - S^{(1)} + S^{(2)} - \dots + (-1)^r S^{(r)} \dots$.

Lemma 1.4. *Suppose there is a constant μ so that $E(X) = S^{(1)} \rightarrow \mu$ and such that for every fixed r ,*

$$E\left(\frac{X^{(r)}}{r!}\right) = S^{(r)} \rightarrow \frac{\mu^r}{r!}.$$

Then $Pr\{X = 0\} \rightarrow \exp(-\mu)$ and, for every t , we have $Pr(X = t) \rightarrow \frac{\mu^t}{t!} \exp(-\mu)$.

In order to prove the theorems we need two lemmas. In the sequel, for the sake of brevity, we write $\mathbf{u} = \{u_1, \dots, u_h\}_m$ and $\mathbf{v} = \{v_1, \dots, v_h\}_m$ with $\mathbf{u} \neq \mathbf{v}$. For every $a \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ and $h, t \in \mathbb{N}, 0 < t \leq h$, let

$$S_{a,h,t} = |\{\mathbf{u} : u_i \in \mathbb{Z}_n \quad \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = a, \quad |\mathbf{u}|_d = t\}|$$

and for every $a_1, a_2 \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ and $h, t, s, k \in \mathbb{N}$ with $0 < k \leq \min\{s, t\}$ let

$$C_{a_1, a_2, h, t, s, k} = \left| \{ \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\} : \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = a_1, \sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a_2, |\mathbf{u}|_d = s, |\mathbf{v}|_d = t, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d = k \} \right|.$$

Lemma 1.5. *For every $a \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ and $h \geq 2$ we have*

1. $S_{a,h,h} = \frac{n^{h-1}}{h!} + O_h(n^{h-2});$
2. $S_{a,h,t} = O_h(n^{t-1})$ for $1 \leq t \leq h - 1$.

Proof. Case (1): By the definition of $S_{a,h,h}$

$$h!S_{a,h,h} = \left| \{(u_1, \dots, u_h) : u_i \in \mathbb{Z}_n, \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = a, \text{ and } u_i \neq u_j \text{ for } i \neq j\} \right|. \quad (1)$$

An upper bound for (1) is $n(n - 1) \dots (n - h + 2)$ and a lower bound is $n(n - 1) \dots (n - h + 3)(n - (h - 2) - (h - 2) - 2)$ because we have $n(n - 1) \dots (n - (h - 3))$ possibilities for u_1, \dots, u_{h-2} and the conditions $u_{h-1} \neq u_i, u_h \neq u_i$ for $1 \leq i \leq h - 2$ and $u_{h-1} \neq u_h$ exclude at most $h - 2 + h - 2 + 2$ choices for u_{h-1} .

Case (2): The condition $|\mathbf{u}|_d = t$ implies that there is a partition $\{1, \dots, h\} = \bigcup_{i=1}^t A_i$ such that $u_i = u_j$ if and only if $1 \leq i, j \leq h$ are in the same A_l . Fix such a partition. Then there are n choices for the elements $u_i, i \in A_1$, then $(n - 1)$ possibilities for the elements $u_i, i \in A_2$ etc. and finally $(n - (t - 2))$ choices for the elements $u_i, i \in A_{t-1}$. It follows from this that if we have already chosen the elements $u_i, i \in \bigcup_{i=1}^{t-1} A_i$ then we have at most $t \leq h$ possibilities for the elements $u_i, i \in A_t$. In order to finish the proof we mention that the number of suitable partitions is $O_h(1)$. \square

Lemma 1.6. *For every $a_1, a_2 \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ and $h \geq 2$ we have*

1. $C_{a_1, a_2, h, h, h, 0} = \frac{n^{2h-2}}{(h!)^{22}} + O_h(n^{2h-3});$
2. $C_{a_1, a_2, h, t, s, k} = O_h(n^{t+s-k-2})$ for $t \geq s$ and $t > k \geq 0;$
3. $C_{a_1, a_2, h, s, s, s} = O_h(n^{s-2})$ for every $2 \leq s < h.$

Proof. Case (1): By the definition of $C_{a_1, a_2, h, h, h, 0}$

$$2(h!)^2 C_{a_1, a_2, h, h, h, 0} = \left| \left\{ ((u_1, \dots, u_h), (v_1, \dots, v_h)) : \begin{array}{l} u_i \neq u_j, v_i \neq v_j, u_i \neq v_j, \\ \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = a_1, \sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a_2 \end{array} \right\} \right|. \quad (2)$$

An upper bound for (2) is $n^{h-1}n^{h-1}$ and a lower bound for (2) is $n(n - 1) \dots (n - (h - 3))(n - (h - 2) - (h - 2) - 2)(n - h)(n - (h + 1)) \dots (n - h - (h - 3))(n - (2h - 2) - (2h - 2) - 2)$, because we have $n(n - 1) \dots (n - (h - 3))$ choices for u_1, \dots, u_{h-2} . After choosing u_1, \dots, u_{h-2} there are at least $n - (h - 2) - (h - 2) - 2$ possibilities left for u_{h-1} because $u_{h-1} \neq u_j$ and $u_h \neq u_j$ for $1 \leq j \leq h - 2$ and $u_{h-1} \neq u_h$. After fixing u_1, \dots, u_h we have $(n - h) \dots (n - (2h - 2))$ choices for v_1, \dots, v_{h-2} . Finally, we have at least $n - 2h - (2h - 4) - 2$ choices for v_{h-1} because $v_{h-1} \neq u_j, v_h \neq u_j$, for $1 \leq j \leq h, v_{h-1} \neq v_j, v_h \neq v_j$ for $1 \leq j \leq h - 2$ and $v_{h-1} \neq v_h$.

Case (2): Obviously,

$$C_{a_1, a_2, h, t, s, k} \leq \left| \left\{ ((u_1, \dots, u_h), (v_1, \dots, v_h)) : \begin{array}{l} \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = a_1, \sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a_2, \\ |\mathbf{u}|_d = t, |\mathbf{v}|_d = s, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d = k \end{array} \right\} \right|. \quad (3)$$

By the conditions $|\mathbf{u}|_d = s, |\mathbf{v}|_d = t$ there are partitions $\{1, \dots, h\} = \cup_{i=1}^t A_i = \cup_{i=1}^s B_i$ such that $u_i = u_j$ if and only if there exists an $1 \leq l \leq t$ such that $i, j \in A_l$, and $v_i = v_j$ if and only if there exists an $1 \leq l \leq s$ such that $i, j \in B_l$. We have at most hn^{s-1} choices for (v_1, \dots, v_h) with $\sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a_2$. The condition $|\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d = k$ implies that there are

injections $\chi_u : \{1, \dots, k\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, t\}$ and $\chi_v : \{1, \dots, k\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, s\}$ such that $u_i = v_j$ if and only if there exists a $1 \leq l \leq k$ such that $u_i \in A_{\chi_u(l)}$ and $v_j \in B_{\chi_v(l)}$. Hence we get that there are at most hn^{t-k-1} choices for the v_i s, $i \in \{1, \dots, h\} \setminus \bigcup_{i=1}^k B_{\chi_v(i)}$. Since the numbers of partitions and injections are $O_h(1)$, the proof is completed.

Case (3): Evidently,

$$C_{a_1, a_2, h, s, s, s} \leq \left| \left\{ ((u_1, \dots, u_h), (v_1, \dots, v_h)) : \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = a_1, \sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a_2, \mathbf{u} \neq \mathbf{v}, \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. |\mathbf{u}|_d = s, |\mathbf{v}|_d = s, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d = s \right\} \right|. \quad (4)$$

By the conditions $|u|_d = s, |v|_d = s$ there are partitions $\{1, \dots, h\} = \bigcup_{i=1}^s A_i = \bigcup_{i=1}^s B_i$ such that $u_i = u_j$ if and only if there exists an $1 \leq l \leq s$ such that $i, j \in A_l$ and $v_i = v_j$ if and only if there exists an $1 \leq m \leq s$ such that $i, j \in B_m$. The condition $|\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d = k$ implies that there is a bijection $\chi : \{1, \dots, s\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, s\}$ such that $u_i = v_j$ if and only if there exists a $1 \leq l \leq s$ such that $i \in A_l$ and $j \in B_{\chi(l)}$. Since $\mathbf{u} \neq \mathbf{v}$, therefore there exists a $1 \leq l \leq s$ such that $|A_l| \neq |B_{\chi(l)}|$. Fix such an l . Then there exists a $1 \leq k \leq s$ such that $\frac{|A_k|}{|B_{\chi(k)}|} \neq \frac{|A_l|}{|B_{\chi(l)}|}$, because otherwise $|A_k| = |B_{\chi(k)}| \frac{|A_l|}{|B_{\chi(l)}|}$ for every $1 \leq k \leq s$, but

$$h = \sum_{k=1}^s |A_k| = \frac{|A_l|}{|B_{\chi(l)}|} \sum_{k=1}^s |B_{\chi(k)}| = \frac{|A_l|}{|B_{\chi(l)}|} h,$$

which is a contradiction. Fix such a k . Let $\{i_1, \dots, i_{s-2}\} = \{1, \dots, s\} \setminus \{k, l\}$. We have $n(n-1) \cdots (n-(s-3))$ choices for the elements $u_i, i \in \bigcup_{j=1}^{s-2} A_{i_j}$. After fixing the

elements $u_i, i \in \bigcup_{j=1}^{s-2} A_{i_j}$ let $\sum_{j=1}^{s-2} \sum_{m \in A_{i_j}} u_m = U$ and $\sum_{j=1}^{s-2} \sum_{m \in B_{\chi(i_j)}} v_m = V$. Then we need

$x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ such that $U + |A_k|x + |A_l|y = a_1$ and $V + |B_{\chi(k)}|x + |B_{\chi(l)}|y = a_2$. Hence,

$$(|A_l||B_{\chi(k)}| - |A_k||B_{\chi(l)}|)y = a_1|B_{\chi(k)}| + V|A_k| - U|B_{\chi(k)}| - a_2|A_k|. \quad (5)$$

After fixing $1 \leq k, l \leq s$ and the elements $u_i, i \in \bigcup_{j=1}^{s-2} A_{i_j}$, the elements U and V are

determined, therefore the right-hand side in (3) is unique. Since $0 < ||A_l||B_{\chi(k)}| - |A_k||B_{\chi(l)}|| \leq h^2$, therefore the number of possible y 's is at most h^2 and after fixing y we have at most h choices for x . Finally we mention that we have got $O_h(1)$ choices for the partitions and bijection. \square

Proof of Theorem 1. For each unordered, different $u_1, \dots, u_h \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ and $v_1, \dots, v_h \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ with $\sum_{i=1}^h u_i = \sum_{i=1}^h v_i$. Let $B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}$ be the event that $u_1, \dots, u_h, v_1, \dots, v_h \in A_n$. In the following we suppose that $\sum_{i=1}^h u_i = \sum_{i=1}^h v_i$. If we prove $\Delta = \sum_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d > 0} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} =$

$o(1)$, then by the Janson inequality we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Pr\{A_n \text{ is } B_h \text{ set}\} &= (1 + o(1)) \prod_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\
 &= (1 + o(1)) \left(\prod_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=h, |\mathbf{v}|_d=h, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=0} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \right) \\
 &\quad \times \left(\prod_{k=1}^{h-1} \prod_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=h, |\mathbf{v}|_d=h, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=k} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \right) \\
 &\quad \times \left(\prod_{s=2}^{h-1} \prod_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=s, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=s} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \right) \\
 &\quad \times \left(\prod_{s=1}^{h-1} \prod_{k=0}^{s-1} \prod_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=s, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=k} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \right) \\
 &\quad \times \left(\prod_{s=1}^{h-1} \prod_{t=s+1}^h \prod_{k=0}^s \prod_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=t, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=k} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \right) \\
 &= P_1 P_2 P_3 P_4 P_5,
 \end{aligned}$$

where, by Lemma 1.6.1,

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_1 &= \prod_{a \in \mathbb{Z}_n} \prod_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=h, |\mathbf{v}|_d=h, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=0, \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = \sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\
 &= \left(1 - \frac{c^{2h}}{n^{2h-1}} \right)^{\frac{n^{2h-1}}{2(h!)^2} (1 + O_h(\frac{1}{n}))} \\
 &= (1 + o(1)) \exp\left(-\frac{c^{2h}}{2(h!)^2}\right),
 \end{aligned}$$

by Lemma 1.6.2,

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_2 &= \prod_{a \in \mathbb{Z}_n} \prod_{k=1}^{h-1} \prod_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=h, |\mathbf{v}|_d=h, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=k, \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = \sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\
 &= \prod_{k=1}^{h-1} (1 - p_n^{2h-k}) O_h(n^{2h-k-1}) \\
 &= \prod_{k=1}^{h-1} \exp\left((p_n n)^{2h-k} O_h\left(\frac{1}{n}\right)\right) \\
 &= \exp(o(1)),
 \end{aligned}$$

by Lemma 1.6.3,

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_3 &= \prod_{a \in \mathbb{Z}_n} \prod_{s=2}^{h-1} \prod_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=s, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=s, \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = \sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\
 &= \prod_{s=2}^{h-1} (1 - p_n^s)^{O_h(n^{s-1})} \\
 &= \prod_{k=1}^h \exp\left((-p_n n)^k O_h\left(\frac{1}{n}\right)\right) \\
 &= \exp(o(1)),
 \end{aligned}$$

by Lemma 1.6.3,

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_4 &= \prod_{a \in \mathbb{Z}_n} \prod_{s=1}^{h-1} \prod_{k=0}^{s-1} \prod_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=s, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=k, \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = \sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\
 &= \prod_{s=1}^h \prod_{k=0}^{s-1} (1 - p_n^{2s-k})^{O_h(n^{2s-k-1})} \\
 &= \prod_{s=1}^h \prod_{k=0}^{s-1} \exp\left(- (p_n n)^{2s-k} O_h\left(\frac{1}{n}\right)\right) \\
 &= \exp(o(1)),
 \end{aligned}$$

and, by Lemma 1.6.2,

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_5 &= \prod_{a \in \mathbb{Z}_n} \prod_{s=1}^{h-1} \prod_{t=s+1}^h \prod_{k=0}^s \prod_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=t, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=k, \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = \sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\
 &= \prod_{s=1}^{h-1} \prod_{t=s+1}^h \prod_{k=0}^s (1 - p_n^{s+t-k})^{O(n^{s+t-k-1})} = \exp(o(1)).
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, it remains to prove that $\Delta = o(1)$. In order to prove $\Delta = o(1)$ we partition Δ as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta &= \sum_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d > 0} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\
 &= \sum_{s=1}^{h-1} \sum_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=s, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=s} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\
 &\quad + \sum_{s=2}^h \sum_{k=1}^{s-1} \sum_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=s, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=k} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\
 &\quad + \sum_{s=1}^{h-1} \sum_{t=s+1}^h \sum_{k=0}^s \sum_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=t, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=k} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\
 &= \sum_1 + \sum_2 + \sum_3.
 \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 1.6.3,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_1 &= \sum_{a \in \mathbb{Z}_n} \sum_{s=1}^{h-1} \sum_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=s, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=s, \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = \sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\ &= \sum_{s=2}^{h-1} O_h(n^{s-1}) p_n^s \\ &= O_h\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{s=2}^{h-1} (p_n n)^s\right) = o(1), \end{aligned}$$

by Lemma 1.6.2,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_2 &= \sum_{a \in \mathbb{Z}_n} \sum_{s=2}^h \sum_{k=1}^{s-1} \sum_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=s, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=k, \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = \sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\ &= \sum_{s=2}^h \sum_{k=1}^{s-1} O_h(n^{2s-k-1}) p_n^{2s-k} \\ &= O_h\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{s=2}^h \sum_{k=1}^{s-1} (p_n n)^{2s-k}\right) = o(1), \end{aligned}$$

and by Lemma 1.6.2,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_3 &= \sum_{a \in \mathbb{Z}_n} \sum_{s=1}^{h-1} \sum_{t=s+1}^h \sum_{k=0}^s \sum_{\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=t, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=k, \sum_{i=1}^h u_i = \sum_{i=1}^h v_i = a} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}}\} \\ &= \sum_{s=1}^{h-1} \sum_{t=s+1}^h \sum_{k=1}^s O_h(n^{t+s-k-1}) p_n^{t+s-k} \\ &= O_h\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{s=1}^{h-1} \sum_{t=s+1}^h \sum_{k=1}^s (p_n n)^{t+s-k}\right) = o(1), \end{aligned}$$

which completes the proof. □

Proof of Theorem 2. For a fixed $x \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ and $y_1, \dots, y_h \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ with $\sum_{i=1}^h y_i = x$ let $\mathbf{y} = \{y_1, \dots, y_h\}$ and let $B_{\mathbf{y}, x}$ be the event $y_1, \dots, y_h \in A_n$. For a fixed $x \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ let $C_x = \bigcap_{\mathbf{y}, \sum_{i=1}^h y_i = x} \overline{B_{\mathbf{y}, x}}$. Obviously,

$$\Pr\{A_n \text{ is an } h\text{-basis}\} = \Pr(\bigcap_{x \in \mathbb{Z}_n} \overline{C_x}).$$

By Lemma 1.4 it is sufficient to show that for every fixed positive integer r we have

$$\sum_{\{x_1, \dots, x_r\}: x_i \in \mathbb{Z}_n, x_i \neq x_j} \Pr\{C_{x_1} \cap \dots \cap C_{x_r}\} \rightarrow \frac{\exp(-rc)}{r!}.$$

In order to estimate

$$\sum_{\{x_1, \dots, x_r\}: x_i \in \mathbb{Z}_n, x_i \neq x_j} \Pr\{C_{x_1} \cap \dots \cap C_{x_r}\} = \sum_{\{x_1, \dots, x_r\}: x_i \in \mathbb{Z}_n, x_i \neq x_j} \Pr\{\cap_{1 \leq i \leq r} \cap_{\mathbf{y}: \sum_{j=1}^h y_j = x_i} \overline{B}_{\mathbf{y}, x_i}\}$$

we use Janson's inequality. Obviously, $\Pr\{B_{\mathbf{y}, x_i}\} = o(1)$. If we prove $\Delta = o(1)$, then by Lemmas 1.3 and 1.5, and the definition of p_n

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\{x_1, \dots, x_r\}: x_i \in \mathbb{Z}_n, x_i \neq x_j} \Pr \left\{ \bigcap_{1 \leq i \leq r} \bigcap_{\mathbf{y}: \sum_{j=1}^h y_j = x_i} \overline{B}_{\mathbf{y}, x_i} \right\} \\ &= (1 + o(1)) \prod_{i=1}^r \prod_{\mathbf{y}: \sum_{j=1}^h y_j = x_i} \Pr\{\overline{B}_{\mathbf{y}, x_i}\} \\ &= (1 + o(1)) \prod_{i=1}^r \prod_{k=1}^h \prod_{\mathbf{y}: y_1 + \dots + y_h = x_i, |\mathbf{u}|_d = k} (1 - p_n^k) \\ &= (1 + o(1)) \prod_{i=1}^r \prod_{k=1}^{h-1} \left((1 - p_n^k)^{O_h(n^{k-1})} \right) (1 - p_n^h)^{\frac{n^{h-1}}{h!} (1 + O_h(\frac{1}{n}))} \\ &= (1 + o(1)) \prod_{i=1}^r \left[\left(\exp \left\{ -O_h \left(\frac{1}{n} \right) \sum_{1 \leq k \leq h-1} (p_n n)^k \right\} \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. \times \left(\exp \left\{ -\frac{(p_n n)^h}{h!} (1 + O_h(p_n^h)) \left(\frac{1}{n} + O_h \left(\frac{1}{n^2} \right) \right) \right\} \right) \right] \\ &= (1 + o(1)) \left(\exp \left\{ -r \frac{h! n \log n (1 + \frac{c}{\log n}) (1 + O_{h,c}(\frac{1}{\log^2 n}))}{h!} \frac{1}{n} \right\} \right) \\ &= (1 + o(1)) \frac{\exp(-cr)}{n^r}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\sum_{\{x_1, \dots, x_r\}, x_i \in \mathbb{Z}_n, x_i \neq x_j} \Pr\{C_{x_1} \cap \dots \cap C_{x_r}\} = (1 + o(1)) \binom{n}{r} \frac{\exp(-cr)}{n^r} = (1 + o(1)) \frac{\exp(-cr)}{r!}.$$

Let $\mathbf{u} = \{u_1, \dots, u_h\}$ with $u_1 + \dots + u_h = x_i$ and $\mathbf{v} = \{v_1, \dots, v_h\}$ with $v_1 + \dots + v_h = x_j$.

In order to finish the proof, we separate Δ as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta &= \sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq r} \sum_{\{\mathbf{u}, x_i\}, \{\mathbf{v}, x_j\}: |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d > 0} \Pr\{B_{\mathbf{u}, x_i} \cap B_{\mathbf{v}, x_j}\} \\ &= \sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq r} \sum_{s=2}^{h-1} \sum_{\{\mathbf{u}, x_i\}, \{\mathbf{v}, x_j\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=s, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=s} p_n^s \\ &\quad + \sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq r} \sum_{s=2}^h \sum_{k=1}^{s-1} \sum_{\{\mathbf{u}, x_i\}, \{\mathbf{v}, x_j\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=s, |\mathbf{u} \cap \mathbf{v}|_d=k} p_n^{2s-k} \\ &\quad + \sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq r} \sum_{s=1}^{h-1} \sum_{t=s+1}^h \sum_{k=1}^s \sum_{\{\mathbf{u}, x_i\}, \{\mathbf{v}, x_j\}: |\mathbf{u}|_d=s, |\mathbf{v}|_d=t, |\mathbf{u} \cap \{v_1, \dots, v_r\}|_d=k} p_n^{s+t-k} \\ &= \sum_1 + \sum_2 + \sum_3, \end{aligned}$$

where, by Lemma 1.6.3,

$$\sum_1 \leq r^2 \sum_{s=2}^{h-1} p_n^s O_h(n^{s-2}) = O_{h,r} \left(\frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{s=2}^{h-1} (p_n n)^s \right) = o(1),$$

by Lemma 1.6.2,

$$\sum_2 \leq r^2 \sum_{s=2}^h \sum_{k=1}^{s-1} p_n^{2s-k} O_h(n^{2s-k-2}) = O_{h,r} \left(\frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{s=2}^h \sum_{k=1}^{s-1} (p_n n)^{2s-k} \right) = o(1),$$

and, by Lemma 1.6.2,

$$\sum_3 \leq r^2 \sum_{s=1}^{h-1} \sum_{t=s+1}^h \sum_{k=1}^s p_n^{t+s-k} O_h(n^{t+s-k}) = O_{h,r} \left(\frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{s=1}^{h-1} \sum_{t=s+1}^h \sum_{k=1}^s (p_n n)^{t+s-k} \right) = o(1)$$

which completes the proof. □

References

- [1] N. ALON, AND J. SPENCER, *The Probabilistic Method*, Wiley-Interscience, Series in Discrete Math. and Optimization, 1992.